

On the morphisms of fractal curves that increase their smoothness.

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Abstract

We propose a construction which transforms a self-similar zipper in \mathbb{R}^n to a self-affine zipper \mathbb{R}^{n+1} whose attractor is a smooth curve.

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Smooth self-affine curves may be constructed in two ways:

1. As it was proved by M. Barnsley [3], for some special types of fractal interpolation functions their integration gives differentiable functions whose graphs are self-affine;
2. The other way is to use the algorithm of building self-affine curves proposed by Alexey Kravchenko [5] in 2005.

We propose one more construction, which transforms a self-similar zipper to a self-affine zipper whose attractor is a smooth curve.

Definition 1. [3] *Let X be a complete metric space. A system $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, \dots, S_m\}$ of contraction mappings of X to itself is called a zipper with vertices $\{z_0, \dots, z_m\}$ and signature $\varepsilon = (\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_m)$, $\varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\}$, if for any $i = 1, \dots, m$, $S_i(z_0) = z_{i-1+\varepsilon_i}$ and $S_i(z_m) = z_{i-\varepsilon_i}$.*

The zipper \mathcal{S} is called self-similar or self-affine, if all S_i are similarities or affine mappings.

Definition 2. [3] *A compact set $K \subset X$ is called an attractor or invariant set of the system \mathcal{S} if*
$$K = \bigcup_{i=1}^n s_i(K).$$

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An attractor of any system exists and unique due to Hutchinson theorem [4]. Attractor of any zipper is arcwise connected and locally arcwise connected [1].

Definition 3. A zipper \mathcal{S} in $[0, 1]$ with vertices $\{0 = t_0, \dots, t_m = 1\}$, is called a line zipper.

Suppose \mathcal{S} is a zipper with vertices $\{z_0, \dots, z_m\}$ and signature ε and γ is its attractor. Let $\mathcal{T} = \{T_1, \dots, T_m\}$ be a line zipper with vertices $\{t_0, \dots, t_m\}$ and signature ε .

As it was proved by Aseev et al [1], there is unique continuous $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow \gamma$ such that $f(t_i) = z_i$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$), and for any $i = 1, \dots, m$ and $t \in [0, 1]$, $f(T_i(t)) = S_i(f(t))$.

Such map f is called a linear parametrization of the zipper \mathcal{S} by the zipper \mathcal{T} .

Proposition 1. Let \mathcal{S} be a self-similar zipper in \mathbb{R}^n with vertices $\{z_0, \dots, z_m\}$ and signature ε , f be its linear parametrization by a line zipper \mathcal{T} with vertices $\{t_0, \dots, t_m\}$. Then $\mathcal{Z} = \{S_1 \times T_1, \dots, S_m \times T_m\}$ is a self-affine zipper in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} with vertices $(z_0, t_0), \dots, (z_m, t_m)$ and signature ε , and its attractor is the graph $\Gamma = \{(t, f(t)), t \in [0, 1]\}$ of the function f . ■

From the construction of the function f it follows that for any $i = 1, \dots, m$ and any $t \in [t_{i-1}, t_i]$

$$f(t) = S_i(f(T_i^{-1}(t))) \text{ where } T_i : [0, 1] \rightarrow [t_{i-1}, t_i] \tag{1}$$

Thus, f can be considered as a fractal interpolation function having variable signature ε . [3,4]

Taking integral of f with respect to t , we obtain a differentiable function $g(t) = \int_0^t f(\tau) d\tau$ on $[0, 1]$, whose graph $\hat{\Gamma} = \{t, g(t)\}$ is a self-affine Jordan arc.

Proposition 2. Let \mathcal{S} be a self-similar zipper in \mathbb{R}^n with vertices $z_0 = 0, \dots, z_m$ and signature ε , and f be its linear parametrization by line zipper \mathcal{T} with vertices t_0, \dots, t_n . Then the graph of the function $g(t) = \int_0^t f(\tau) d\tau$ is the attractor of a self-affine zipper in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} with the signature ε .

Proof. Put $z_m = b, g(1) = h$.

$$\text{We write } S_i(z) = \begin{cases} z_{i-1} + A_i z, & \text{if } \varepsilon_i = 0 \\ z_i - A_i z, & \text{if } \varepsilon_i = 1 \end{cases}.$$

Here A_i are the similarities sending $0, b$ to 0 and $z_i - z_{i-1}$ respectively. Denote by q_i the contraction ratio $t_i - t_{i-1}$ of T_i . Then the function f satisfies the equations:

$$f(t) = \begin{cases} z_{i-1} + A_i f((t - t_{i-1})/q_i), & \text{if } \varepsilon_i = 0 \\ z_{i-1} + A_i (b - f((t_i - t)/q_i)), & \text{if } \varepsilon_i = 1 \end{cases} \text{ for } t \in [t_{i-1}, t_i] \tag{2}$$

Integrating from t_{i-1} to t , we obtain:

$$g(t) - g(t_{i-1}) = \begin{cases} z_{i-1}(t - t_{i-1}) + q_i A_i g((t - t_{i-1})/q_i) & \text{if } \varepsilon_i = 0, \\ z_i(t - t_{i-1}) + q_i A_i (g((t_i - t)/q_i) - h) & \text{if } \varepsilon_i = 1 \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

$$g(t_i) - g(t_{i-1}) = \begin{cases} z_{i-1} q_i + q_i A_i h, & \varepsilon_i = 0 \\ z_i q_i - q_i A_i h, & \varepsilon_i = 1 \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

Taking the sum for all i , we see that h satisfies:

$$\left(Id - \sum_{i=1}^m (-1)^{\varepsilon_i} q_i A_i \right) h = \sum_{i=1}^m q_i z_{i-1+\varepsilon_i} \tag{5}$$

Finding h from this equation we find the values of all $g(t_i)$.

From the equation 3 we see that the graph $\tilde{\Gamma}$ of the map g is the attractor of $\mathcal{Z} = \{W_1, \dots, W_m\}$, where

$$W_i(\tilde{z}) = \begin{pmatrix} t_{i-1+\varepsilon_i} \\ g(t_{i-1+\varepsilon_i}) \end{pmatrix} + (-1)^{\varepsilon_i} q_i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ z_{i-1+\varepsilon_i}, 1 & & & \\ \dots & & (-1)^{\varepsilon_i} A_i & \\ z_{i-1+\varepsilon_i}, n & & & \end{pmatrix} \tilde{z}$$

This shows that \mathcal{Z} is a self-affine zipper with vertices $(t_i, g(t_i))$ and signature ε . ■

Proposition 3. *The projection of $\tilde{\Gamma}$ to \mathbb{R}^n is smooth at any point, except 0.*

Proof. The projection of $\tilde{\Gamma}$ to \mathbb{R}^n is $\{g(t) : t \in [0, 1]\}$. Taking $g'(t) = f(t)$ we obtain $g'(t) = 0$ only when $t = 0$. ■

In this paper we consider the simplest zippers consisting of two mappings.

Example 1. First, consider the line zipper, consisting of the similarities $S_1 : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, p]$ and $S_2 : [0, 1] \rightarrow [p, 1]$, where $0 < p < 1$. Obviously, its attractor is the segment $[0, 1]$. Parametrize it so that $f\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = p$. The graph of this parameterization is the attractor of the zipper on the plane, consisting of two mappings that transform a single square in the rectangles $\left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right] \times [0, p]$ and $\left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \times [p, 1]$ (Fig. 1).

Figure 1.

The parameterization of zipper satisfies equation:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} pf(2x), x \in \left[0; \frac{1}{2}\right] \\ (1-p)f(2x-1) + p, x \in \left[\frac{1}{2}; 1\right] \end{cases}$$

Let $g(x) = \int_0^x f(\xi)d\xi$.

Then $g(x)$ satisfies equation:

$$g(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{p}{2}g(2x), x \in \left[0; \frac{1}{2}\right] \\ \frac{(1-p)}{2}g(2x-1) + pt + \frac{p(p-1)}{2}, x \in \left[\frac{1}{2}; 1\right] \end{cases}$$

The zipper that specifies the graph (Fig. 2) of the function $g(x)$ consists of :

$$\begin{cases} W_1(x, y) = \left(\frac{x}{2}; \frac{p}{2}y\right) \\ W_2(x, y) = \left(\frac{x}{2} + \frac{1}{2}; \frac{1-p}{2}y + \frac{p}{2}x + \frac{p^2}{2}\right) \end{cases}$$

Figure 2.

Put $y_i = f(x_i)$, $p_i = \frac{y_i - y_{i-1}}{y_m}$, $y_0 = 0$, $q_i = x_i - x_{i-1}$ for $i = 0, 1, 2$. Then

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} p_1 f\left(\frac{x}{q_1}\right) \\ p_2 f\left(\frac{x-x_1}{q_2}\right) + y_1 \end{cases}, \quad g(x) = \begin{cases} p_1 q_1 g\left(\frac{x}{q_1}\right) \\ p_2 q_2 g\left(\frac{x-x_1}{q_2}\right) + y_1(x-x_1) + p_1 q_1 g(1) \end{cases},$$

where $g(1) = \frac{y_1 q_2}{1 - p_1 q_1 - p_2 q_2}$.

It seems that we can derive the points y_1, y_2 from $g_i = g(x_i)$:

$$y_1 = \left(\frac{1}{q_1} - \frac{1}{q_2}\right) g_1 + \left(\frac{1}{q_2} - 1\right) g_2, \quad y_2 = \frac{q_1 g_2}{g_1} y_1.$$

So, to construct a zipper with the vertices $(0, 0)$, (x_1, g_1) , $(1, g_2)$ and the signature $\varepsilon = (0, 0)$ with smooth attractor, we can take

$$W_1(x, y) = \left(\frac{x}{q_1}, \frac{g_1}{g_2}y\right),$$

$$W_2(x, y) = \left(\frac{x}{q_2} + x_1, \left(1 - \frac{g_1}{q_1 g_2}\right) q_2 y + \left(\left(\frac{1}{q_1} - \frac{1}{q_2}\right) g_1 + \left(\frac{1}{q_2} - 1\right) g_2\right) \left(\frac{x-x_1}{q_2} - x_1\right) + g_1\right).$$

Example 2. Consider another case of zipper on the plane, consisting of:

$$\begin{cases} S_1 \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = pA \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \\ S_2 \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = pB \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ h \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

where $0 < h < \sqrt{3}/2$, $p = \sqrt{h^2 + \frac{1}{4}}$, $\alpha = \arctan(2h)$, A and B are the rotation matrixes:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & -\sin \alpha \\ \sin \alpha & \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix}.$$

However, $S_1 : [0, 1] \times [0, 0] \rightarrow \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right] \times [0, h]$, $S : [0, 1] \times [0, 0] \rightarrow \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \times [0, h]$.

Parametrize zipper so that $f\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \begin{pmatrix} 1/2 \\ h \end{pmatrix}$:

$$f(t) = \begin{cases} pAf(2t), t \in \left[0; \frac{1}{2}\right] \\ pBf(2t-1) + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ h \end{pmatrix}, t \in \left[\frac{1}{2}; 1\right] \end{cases}$$

Let $g(t) = \int_0^t f(\xi)d\xi$.

Then:

$$g(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{p}{2}Ag(2t), t \in \left[0; \frac{1}{2}\right] \\ \frac{p}{2}Bg(2t-1) + \frac{p}{2}A \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2(1-p\cos\alpha)} \\ \frac{1}{1-p\cos\alpha} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{t}{2} \\ ht \end{pmatrix}, t \in \left[\frac{1}{2}; 1\right] \end{cases}$$

The corresponding zipper consists of two mappings that transform unit cube into a rectangular parallelepiped $\left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right] \times \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right] \times [0, h]$ and $\left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \times \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \times [0, h]$:

$$\begin{cases} W_1 \begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{t}{2} \\ \frac{p}{2}A \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \\ W_2 \begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{t}{2} \\ ht \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{t}{2} \\ \frac{p}{2}B \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

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